

An Open Source, Parallel, and Distributed Web-Based Probabilistic Risk Assessment Platform to Support Real Time Nuclear Power Plant Risk-Informed Operational Decisions

Milestone Report

Task 1: Literature Review, Benchmarking, and Profiling of Current Probabilistic Risk Assessment (PRA) Tools

Egemen M. Aras, Asmaa S. Farag, Arjun Earthperson, S. Ted Wood (INL), Jordan T. Boyce (INL), Mihai A. Diaconeasa

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Executive Summary

This milestone report lays the foundation for research on improving PRA tools, focusing on the literature review and introducing a diagnostics methodology for PRA tools. The rest of the research will build on the findings presented in this report.

In addition to the literature review, the methodology was demonstrated using the legacy tool SAPHIRE and the open-source tool SCRAM. As a result, the research community can now test their tools based on the methodology provided in this report with minimal effort.

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Disclaimer

The content of this report is largely a combination of various project outcomes, including conference papers, a master's thesis, and a Ph.D. dissertation.

Outcomes of the Project

The project contributes to the research environment in various ways, and the outcomes are listed below for reference. In addition to the listed outcomes, two journal papers are ready for submission, and one report covering the SAPHIRE post-processing engine is under review. Furthermore, North Carolina State University and Idaho National Laboratory have established a highly efficient collaborative environment.

1.1 Conference Papers

1. Benchmark Study of XFTA and SCRAM Fault Tree Solvers Using Synthetically Generated Fault Tree Models [1]
2. Methodology and Demonstration for Performance Analysis of a Probabilistic Risk Assessment Quantification Engine: SCRAM [2]
3. Method of Developing a SCRAM Parallel Engine for Efficient Quantification of Probabilistic Risk Assessment Models [3]
4. Introducing OpenPRA: A Web-Based Framework for Collaborative Probabilistic Risk Assessment [4]
5. Evaluating PRA Tools for Accurate and Efficient Quantifications: A Follow-up Benchmarking Study Including FTREX [5]
6. Introducing OpenPRA's Quantification Engine: Exploring Capabilities, Recognizing Limitations, and Charting the Path to Enhancement [6]
7. Enhancing the SAPHIRE Solve Engine: Initial Progress and Efforts [7]
8. Advancing SAPHIRE: Transitioning from Legacy to State-of-Art Excellence [8]
9. Towards a Deep-Learning Based Heuristic for Optimal Variable Ordering in Binary Decision Diagrams to Support Fault Tree Analysis [9]

1.2 Journal Papers

1. A Critical Look at the Need for Performing Multi-Hazard Probabilistic Risk Assessment for Nuclear Power Plants [10]

1.3 Reports

1. Refining Processing Engines from SAPHIRE: Initialization of Fault Tree/Event Tree Solver [11]

1.4 Master's Thesis

1. Benchmarking Study of Probabilistic Risk Assessment Tools Using Synthetically Generated Fault Tree Models: SAPHSOLVE, XFTA, and SCRAM [12]

1.5 Ph.D. Dissertation

1. Enhancement Methodology for Probabilistic Risk Assessment Tools through Optimization and Parallel Computing [13]

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
BDD	Binary Decision Diagram
BN	Bayesian Network
CD	Core Damage
ETA	Event Tree Analysis
ETL	Event Tree Linking
FTA	Fault Tree Analysis
FTL	Fault Tree Linking
GUI	Graphical User Interface
INES	International Nuclear Event Scale
INL	Idaho National Laboratory
JSCut	JSON Output File
JSInp	JSON Input File
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LBLOCA	Large Break Loss of Cooling
LLNL	Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory
LWR	Light Water Reactor
MCS	Minimal Cut Sets
MCUB	Min Cut Upper Bound
NCSU	North Carolina State University
NPP	Nuclear Power Plant
NRC	Nuclear Regulatory Commission
PC	Personal Computer
PRA	Probabilistic Risk Assessment
PRAG	Probabilistic Risk Assessment Group
PSA	Probabilistic Safety Assessment
REA	Rare-Event Approximation
SAPHSOLVE	SAPHIRE Solve Engine
SDP	Sum of Disjoint Products
US	United States
WHO	World Health Organization
XML	Extensible Markup Language
ZBDD	Zero-Suppressed Binary Decision Diagram

1 Literature Review, Benchmarking, and Profiling of Current Probabilistic Risk Assessment Tools

1.1 Overview of the Report

This report marks a significant milestone in the overall project. As a reminder, the project consists of five main tasks outlined below. This milestone report presents the outcomes of the first task:

- Task 1: Literature review, benchmarking, and profiling of current PRA tools
- Task 2: Design and implementation
- Task 3: Testing and benchmarking for serial and parallel improvements
- Task 4: Application to real-world PRA models
- Task 5: Verification and documentation

The remainder of the report is as follows: Section 1.2 summarizes the history of PRA tools and highlights current issues. Section 1.3 introduces common PRA model structures. Section 1.4 discusses how to quantify a model. Section 1.5 provides an overview of multi-hazard PRA models. Section 1.6 presents the benchmarking and standard profiling results for SCRAM and SAPHIRE Solve Engine (SAPHSOLVE). The report is concluded in Section 1.7.

1.2 Probabilistic Risk Assessment Tools and Issues

In the evolution of PRA during the 1970s, various tools, as shown in Figure 1, were concurrently developed to facilitate the analysis process. Here is a list of some notable PRA tools:

- **PREP and KITT [14]:** Developed as computer code for automatically evaluating a fault tree by Idaho Nuclear Corporation. PREP obtained minimal cut sets (MCS) of the fault tree using either Monte Carlo or deterministic methods, while KITT obtained numerical probabilities associated with the tree.
- **MOCUS [15]:** Developed by Aerojet Nuclear Company, MOCUS is a computer program to obtain minimal cut sets from fault trees.
- **MODULE [16]:** A computer program capable of handling minimal cut set generation, importance analysis, and uncertainty analysis.

- **SIGPI [17]:** A computer program developed by Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory (LLNL) for the Nuclear Regulatory Commission (NRC) computes complex systems' probability.
- **CAFTA [18]:** Develop, maintain, and update single-top failure models through fault and event tree modeling. It is currently maintained under the Phoenix Architect Module [19] and is mainly used by the United States (US) Nuclear Power Plant (NPP) owners.
- **SAPHIRE [20], [21]:** A follow-up work of IRRAS [22], an application developed by the Idaho National Laboratory (INL) for the NRC, released in 1987. SAPHIRE is widely used for performing complete PRA using personal computers and is one of the most used PRA tools in the US.
- **RISKMAN [23]:** A personal computer (PC) based, general-purpose, integrated tool for quantitative risk analysis developed by ABS Consulting, Inc [24].
- **KIRAP [25]:** A fault tree construction and analysis code package.
- **RiskSpectrum [26]:** An advanced software developed by Relcon Scandpower AB, increasingly used for developing fault trees and event trees to assess system reliability in various parts of NPP.
- **RiskA [27]:** An integrated reliability and PRA tool developed by the FDS Team.
- **XFTA [28]:** A calculation engine initially developed in 2012 as part of the Open-PSA initiative.
- **SCRAM [29]:** An open-source, command-line risk analysis multi-tool currently under enhancement in the PRAG in the Nuclear Engineering Department at North Carolina State University (NCSU).
- **DeRisk [30]:** A dynamic, uncertain causality graph-embedded risk analysis code package.

To summarize, numerous PRA tools have been developed and continuously improved. CAFTA is the preferred choice for most NPP operators in the US. SAPHIRE is the NRC's primary software tool for modeling, evaluating, and validating NPP results. Meanwhile, SCRAM is a versatile open-source PRA tool that can perform nearly all PRA calculations.

Figure 1. PRA tools developed along the history.

Although significant improvements have been made, there is still much room for enhancement in PRA tools to efficiently utilize resources and obtain accurate results in a shorter time. Below are some of the current areas that need improvement [31] in PRA tools:

- Quantification time and efficiency
 - Extremely long quantification times may tax the quantification engine, leading to extended waiting periods and eventual quantification failure due to memory limitations.
 - Fire PRA models are significantly larger than typical internal-events models and come with quantification challenges.
- Dependency analysis for human reliability analysis
- Model development, maintenance, and updates
 - The manual, labor-intensive process is error-prone and should be automated.

- Model manipulation, often done through flag settings in text files, is time-consuming, inefficient, and prone to error.
- Risk aggregation
 - Multi-hazard models:
 - Internal-events models often rely on rare-event approximations, which may be inadequate for external events such as earthquakes, high winds, and external flooding, where fragilities of Systems, Structures, and Components (SSC) are typically higher.
 - Accurate probability conditions in modern seismic PRA result in quickly exhausting memory without using rare-event approximations.
 - Multi-unit sites:
 - Current PRA models assume independence among units on a site, but many resources are shared among units.
 - Analyzing combinations of PRA model elements for criticality.
 - Uncertainty analysis:
 - Currently, parametric uncertainty is applied only, but more details are needed to understand the missing components.
 - Communication of risk insight:
 - Communicating PRA information to non-PRA practitioners has been a longstanding challenge in the industry.
 - Incorporating new PRA technologies into existing models.

This project addresses quantification speed, efficiency, model development, maintenance, and updates. Additionally, we discuss risk aggregation, specifically multi-hazard PRA models.

1.3 Probabilistic Risk Assessment Model Structure

PRA model generation is a crucial step in the design, operation, and even decommissioning phases of an NPP. As listed in the previous chapter, various tools are available to model the system and quantify the model. Almost all PRA tools have their methods for model generation and maintenance. Understanding how the tool generates the model, stores it, and how it could be exchanged with another PRA tool is the initial

step to enhancing a PRA tool. Throughout this research, we use SAPHIRE and SCRAM to demonstrate our findings.

This section delves into SAPHISOLVE (Section 1.3.1) and Open-PSA [32] MEF (Section 1.3.2), which is compatible with SCRAM.

1.3.1 SAPHISOLVE Models

This subsection overviews SAPHIRE and highlights its input and output formats.

1.3.1.1 Overview of SAPHIRE

SAPHIRE is a well-established and comprehensively documented software package featuring a seven-volume manual [20] and technical reference:

- **Volume 1:** Summarizes the other volumes and provides an overview of SAPHIRE's capabilities.
- **Volume 2:** Serves as a technical reference, covering set-theoretic concepts, a review of fault tree logic, probability concepts, determination of minimal cut sets, quantification tools for probabilities and frequencies, event probability calculation types, importance measures, uncertainty, and seismic calculations.
- **Volume 3:** A user guide systematically explaining each feature of SAPHIRE.
- **Volume 4:** A tutorial detailing the overall process of constructing a PRA database using a simple modeling domain, with most of SAPHIRE's features discussed along the way.
- **Volume 5:** Guides users through three types of workspaces available in SAPHIRE.
- **Volume 6:** Covers the software's quality assurance methods, tests, and configuration control.
- **Volume 7:** Crucial for understanding data loading, conversion methods, and related issues, including validation.

SAPHIRE's core functionality extends beyond modeling systems using event trees and fault trees, encompassing the generation and quantification of cut sets for specified truncation values. Numerous methods and features have been implemented to facilitate risk-informed decision-making.

Users can input basic event data, construct, and solve fault trees and event trees, conduct uncertainty analyses along with importance analysis, and generate various reports using the SAPHIRE graphical user interface (GUI). Despite being developed and primarily maintained for the NRC, SAPHIRE has gained widespread adoption nationally and

internationally. Notably, the aerospace industry, including NASA, relies on SAPHIRE to make risk-informed decisions beyond its application in the nuclear industry.

The SAPHIRE Application Programming Interface (API) seamlessly integrates nine engines, each designed for a specific function. Users can initiate various actions through the graphical user interface to create models and input data.

Here is a refined summary of each engine's functions, along with their respective inputs and outputs:

- **Fault Tree Solver:** Receives fault tree logic and basic event information as input, generating cut sets. Users can select the cut set generation algorithm and define value and size truncation parameters for evaluating failure probabilities.
- **Event Tree/Sequence Solver:** Solves event trees, evaluating end states, cut sets, and their values, such as Core Damage Frequency.
- **Cut Set Post-Processor:** Updates cut sets, failure probabilities, and end-state frequency without regenerating cut sets using Rule Files comprising if-else statements and various actions.
- **Cut Set Updater:** Reevaluates existing cut sets after post-processing to remove potential non-minimal cut sets, ensuring the final results are accurate.
- **Event Tree Linker:** Establishes logical relationships and dependencies between events and outcomes within event trees, defining how events are connected and how the system responds to different paths of events.
- **Cut Set Partition Processor:** Partitions event tree/sequence cut sets into end states based on predefined rules.
- **Change Set Processor:** Updates basic event failure information based on provided change sets.
- **Uncertainty Sampler:** Performs uncertainty analysis using Monte Carlo and Latin Hypercube methods on fault trees, sequences, end states, and importance measures.
- **End-State Gather:** Gathers cut sets from event tree/sequences into end states for further analysis.

Given our focus on model generation, the Fault Tree Solver and Event Tree/Sequence Solver engines are of particular interest for this paper. Together, they comprise the SAPHIRE quantification engine, commonly called SAPH SOLVE. SAPH SOLVE is aimed to function as an independent and remote solver for a proposed web-based SAPHIRE platform.

1.3.1.2 SAPHSOLVE Model Structure

After a thorough evaluation of available options, it is determined that utilizing JavaScript Object Notation [33] (JSON) would best meet the requirements of the remote solver. This choice was based on JSON's lightweight and versatile nature as a data-interchange format. Its ability to encapsulate essential data and facilitate seamless communication between the remote solver and its components made it the ideal candidate for creating input and output files. This strategic decision ensured that SAPHSOLVE could effectively execute its designated functions and produce results that could be analyzed and compared against those generated by the internal integrated solver.

The adoption of JSON for structuring input and output files highlights a commitment to precision and efficiency in remote solving, demonstrating a proactive approach to accommodating technological advancements while preserving compatibility and reliability. This strategic choice serves as a cornerstone in the ongoing refinement and advancement of SAPHIRE's capabilities, solidifying its position as a leading tool in PRA.

A recent report on SAPHSOLVE input and output files are published through INL [11]. The following section emphasizes only critical aspects of this report.

a. Input File Specification

The input file utilizes the *JSInp* extension; nomenclature is chosen to distinctly identify these files from their output counterparts, *JSCut*. It contains crucial logic and foundational data of event failures essential for generating cut sets. This file format encapsulates all pertinent details for resolving fault or event tree sequences.

Figure 2 illustrates the comprehensive framework of an input file utilized by SAPHSOLVE's *Header* sub-block, which summarizes the model and truncation parameters. At the same time, the *System gate list* offers details specific to the fault tree model. The *Fault tree list* comprises information regarding each fault tree logic, and the *Sequence list* pertains to event tree models, delineating failure scenarios. Additionally, the *Event list* encompasses all basic event failure rates and initiating event frequencies. Due to the extensive nature of these models, they are not presented in the report as text; however, all SAPHSOLVE models developed and analyzed are accessible through the repository [34].

In fault tree scenarios, each *JSInp* file corresponds to a single fault tree containing relevant information specific to that tree. In event tree scenarios, a *JSInp* file encompasses a combination of fault tree logic, sequences, and logical constructs derived from combinations within the fault tree. This combination defines event tree accident sequences, supplemented by fundamental event particulars necessary for deriving cut sets.

Figure 2. General structure of the SAPH SOLVE input file.

b. Output File Specification

SAPH SOLVE generates cut sets based on the input file provided, which are then returned in a JSON-based *JSCut* file. This file contains the cut sets and information about their origin and the truncation parameters utilized during their generation. It provides details such as the total count of cut sets and their cumulative failure value for each fault tree or sequence within an event tree.

Figure 3 illustrates the general structure of the output file. The *General information* sub-block summarizes the solution, including details such as the version number and file path. The *Truncation parameters* sub-block encompasses the input truncation parameters utilized in the analysis. The *Workspace pair* sub-block specifies the phase and model type. Results are accessible through the *Sequence list results*, which includes the outcomes for each sequence. Information such as the number of cut sets, failure probability, and the list of cut sets is provided for each sequence.

Figure 3. General structure of the SAPHISOLVE output file.

1.3.2 Open-PSA Model Exchange Framework

The Open-PSA MEF was initiated in 2007, with the last modification made in 2017 by the Open Initiative for Next Generation PSA. The primary objective was establishing a software-independent model representation, enabling seamless sharing of models and industry data across various PSA (PRA) software platforms while preserving each software's internal representation.

XML (Extensible Markup Language) was selected as the document type to represent models due to its widespread use for data sharing on the Internet. Additionally, XML's structured nature allows explicitly naming each construct, facilitating clarity and interoperability.

The current version of SCRAM supports the Open-PSA format. Below, brief information about SCRAM is given, along with the model structure.

1.3.2.1 Overview of SCRAM

SCRAM, a robust PRA quantification engine, is currently undergoing enhancements by the PRAG at NCSU [35]. The initial development of SCRAM was contributed by its developer from 2014 to 2019.

While SCRAM lacks a reliable GUI, it possesses the functionality necessary for a PRA tool. It is more akin to SAPH SOLVE than SAPHIRE, as SAPHIRE comprises a toolset detailed in the previous section.

SCRAM excels in event tree and fault tree quantification. It can generate cut sets from a provided model, calculate failure probabilities, assess importance measures, and conduct uncertainty calculations using Monte Carlo simulations. It operates solely through a command-line interface, accepting input files and configurations via command-line commands.

1.3.2.2 SCRAM Model Structure

SCRAM adheres to the Open-PSA MEF for input and output, following a four-plus-one layer architecture outlined in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Architecture of the model exchange format [32].

The innermost layer, known as the stochastic layer, encompasses probability distributions for the failure rates of basic events, along with the parameters of these distributions and the distribution of these parameters. Next is the fault tree layer, housing the model logic, which serves as the heart of the model. The meta-logical layer includes common-cause

groups, delete terms, and recovery rules. The event tree layer comprises initiating events and consequences. Finally, the report layer stores the calculated results.

1.4 Probabilistic Risk Assessment Model Quantification

Model quantification in PRA can be divided into two approaches: the classical approach, based on the computation of MCS, and the Binary Decision Diagrams (BDD). The classical approach, unchanged since the *WASH 1400* study, is implemented in most PRA tools. Due to the PRA models' large size and complexity, various approximations are made for the classical approach. These include truncation in MCS, probability calculation approximations, and the treatment of success branches in event trees and negations [36].

On the other hand, BDDs are compact data structures that enable quantification of models without approximation. However, this comes at a significant computational cost, and it may not be possible to quantify large models using BDDs with the available computing resources.

1.4.1 Event Tree Quantification

Event tree analysis (ETA) is used to identify the consequences when an undesired event has occurred. In addition to the nuclear industry, ETA applies to chemical processing, offshore oil-gas production, and transportation. ETA is an inductive technique that examines all possible responses to the initiating event, progressing left to right across the page. A simple event tree example [37] is given in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Simple event tree example for demonstrating purpose.

The event tree serves as a representation of mitigation systems for an undesired event. In Figure 5, the initiating event, denoted as Event I, represents the occurrence of the undesired event. Systems S1 and S2 are mitigation systems, or engineering functions, designed to mitigate the undesired end-state, which could be core damage (CD) in the context of an NPP. The event tree is constructed by branching when encountering a mitigation system. The upper branch represents success, while the lower branch

represents failure of that safety system. Since there are various safety functions, not all sequences end up with the undesired event. The goal of quantifying an event tree is to evaluate the failure probability of the undesired end-state sequence.

Each mitigation system has its failure probability for the given initiating event, typically determined by a fault tree specific to that system. Examples of demonstration fault trees for a simple event tree are provided in Figure 6 and Figure 7.

Figure 6. System 1 fault tree.

Figure 7. System 2 fault tree.

To better understand how the quantification of an event tree works, we can begin by writing the necessary equations for each end state. Eqn. (1) through (4) represent each end-state of a simple event tree, where E_i stands for the i^{th} end state, and S_i represents the given mitigation system, a qualitative representation of each end state, presented as a Boolean equation.

$$E_1 = \bar{S}_1 \cdot \bar{S}_2 \quad (1)$$

$$E_2 = \bar{S}_1 \cdot S_2 \quad (2)$$

$$E_3 = S_1 \cdot \bar{S}_2 \quad (3)$$

$$E_4 = S_1 \cdot S_2 \quad (4)$$

The related end states should be multiplied by the initiating event frequency to obtain quantitative results, represented through Eqn. (5) to (8). Additionally, the * symbol denotes multiplication, while the \cdot symbol represents the *AND* boolean operator. An initial challenge lies in obtaining the failure probabilities of safety systems derived from fault tree analysis (FTA), which will be detailed in the next section.

$$P(E_1) = f * P(\bar{S}_1) \cdot P(\bar{S}_2) \quad (5)$$

$$P(E_2) = f * P(\bar{S}_1) \cdot P(S_2) \quad (6)$$

$$P(E_3) = f * P(S_1) \cdot P(\bar{S}_2) \quad (7)$$

$$P(E_4) = f * P(S_1) \cdot P(S_2) \quad (8)$$

One significant aspect to consider in event tree quantification is how to approach success branches. The classical PRA approach does not handle negations directly, as MCS does not contain negative literals. One expected solution involves treating these negations as

logical complements in generating MCS. However, negations significantly slow down the Boolean reduction process, making it impractical.

A straightforward workaround is to ignore success branches, treating the sequence as coherent. Another approximation involves correcting the previous one by introducing a factor that computes the probability of success. A third and more effective approximation, used in many PRA tools [38], is the delete-term approximation. This method entails removing from the set of minimal cut sets of the coherent sequence those cut sets contained in any cut set of the negated top event. Since event tree quantification is inherently tied to fault tree quantification, it is essential to delve into the quantification of fault trees. The following section will explore current approaches, various approximations, and newly developed algorithms in fault tree quantification.

1.4.2 Fault Tree Quantification

Overall, fault tree quantification can be classified in various ways. It may be categorized into two main approaches: computation of MCS and sum of disjoint products (SDP).

In the first approach, MCS is obtained either with or without truncation in size, and then the probability is calculated based on the obtained MCS. Probability calculation is often approximated using methods like rare-event approximation (REA) or min-cut upper bound (MCUB).

The computation of MCS is a fundamental aspect of most PRA tools. The objective is to generate MCS from the given model while considering specific specifications. These specifications may involve size truncation in MCS, approximation in probability calculation, and truncation in probability value. Each specification represents a trade-off between achieving accurate results and computational efficiency.

The Boolean equation, which forms the basis of MCS generation, grows exponentially with the number of variables, particularly in the context of NPP PRA models. Therefore, it is essential to eliminate MCSs that make negligible contributions to risk estimates. Initial truncation may be applied during the generation of cut sets by assigning a truncation value in size, limiting the size of the cut sets for subsequent processing.

A second truncation may be applied during probability calculation from the obtained cut sets, which could be a regulatory or design limit, such as 10^{-8} per year. However, exact probability calculation from generated cut sets is often infeasible due to the complexity of considering every term in the inclusion-exclusion formula. Hence, approximations like REA and MCUB are commonly employed.

While truncations and approximations enhance computational efficiency, they also introduce errors, deviating from exact results. For example, such approximations are

generally acceptable when failure rates are less than 0.1. However, as failure rates increase or models incorporate negations, the discrepancy between exact and approximated results may become significant, reaching up to a 98% probability overestimation [39].

On the other hand, probability can be directly calculated from the model without computing MCS, resulting in exact probabilities in SDP.

Also, fault tree quantification methods can be classified based on how the solution is handled; it may involve bottom-up or top-down algorithms. For instance, MOCUS, detailed below, is a top-down approach, while BDD and zero-suppressed binary decision diagram (ZBDD) are bottom-up.

Each fault tree quantification approach has three pillars: pre-processing, quantification, and post-processing. The pre-processing step involves validating and preparing the fault tree for generating cut sets, which may include reducing or modularizing the fault tree. Quantification involves generating cut sets, calculating the top event probability, and applying any necessary truncation. Post-processing includes evaluating importance factors, quantifying uncertainty, updating cut sets, and re-evaluating failure probabilities based on the results obtained.

During the pre-processing of the fault tree, it is converted into a format ready for solving, making subsequent steps more efficient. Different solvers employ various algorithms for this stage, intending to prepare the fault tree for the solution. Pre-processing tasks [22] may include validating basic events and gates, checking failure data, expanding transfer gates, determining the top gate, converting complement gates, pruning house events, modularizing the fault tree, and leveling the fault tree. By the end of the pre-processing stage, the fault tree is restructured and ready for solution.

Choosing the appropriate method involves a scientific tradeoff considering expectations and available resources. The quantification step is pivotal and can significantly impact results if misapplied. Post-processing of the fault tree is crucial for evaluating the importance factors and uncertainty. Key importance factors [40] include Fussell-Vesely, risk reduction ratio, risk increase ratio, Birnbaum, risk reduction interval, risk increase interval, and structural importance. These importance factors, along with uncertainty, MCS, and failure probabilities, can inform risk-informed decisions and are collectively called risk metrics.

1.4.3 Quantification of Event Tree Combined with Fault Tree

Combining an event and fault tree is a modeling strategy and may depend on the available software, system, and knowledge. Fault tree linking (FTL) and event tree linking (ETL)

are different approaches to performing PRA [41]. FTL is called the small event tree-large fault tree approach, and ETL is called the large event tree-small fault tree approach [42].

The FTL approach, as utilized in the *WASH-1400* and subsequent studies sponsored by the US NRC, follows a series of crucial steps:

- **Construct Event Trees:** Develop an event tree for each initiating event, delineating the potential accident sequences.
- **Build Fault Trees:** Create fault trees for each front-line system, which includes safety systems or engineering functions identified in the event tree. Additionally, support systems for these front-line systems within the fault trees should be incorporated.
- **Define Event Sequences:** Express the event sequences regarding front-line system successes and failures. Manage success branches according to the preferred method, such as the delete-term approximation technique.
- **Evaluate Cut Sets:** Examine the cut sets for each accident sequence, assessing factors like consistency, recovery potential, and timing considerations.
- **Determine Component Failure Probability:** Obtain final component failure probabilities, such as CDF, based on the analyzed data.

In the FTL approach, dependencies at the sequence level are identified through the Boolean reduction process, ensuring that any dependencies are accurately modeled and corrected within the system fault trees. This meticulous approach ensures that the analysis captures the intricacies and interdependencies of the system components, providing insights into the overall safety and reliability of the system under study.

The ETL approach offers an alternative method for analyzing event trees akin to the FTL approach. The fundamental principle behind ETL is to organize the event tree to reduce the size and interdependencies of system failure models within a sequence. This involves introducing additional top events to the event tree and modeling front-line systems as trains, with support systems included. By doing so, the system failure models become smaller and lack support system dependencies. Concurrently, models for support system failures are developed, ensuring that components are contained within one top event logic model for a given accident sequence.

Compared to FTL event trees, ETL event trees tend to be larger, with each event tree top event featuring more branch points. Each branch point is associated with success criteria, determined by the preceding top events in the accident sequence. The objective is to estimate each branch point's conditional split fraction, or top event probability, employing suitable techniques tailored to the specific criteria. One common method is to create logic models for the branch points, quantifying them independently since they are separate

from other top event logic models in the accident sequence. This independence ensures that each logic model contains components unique to its branch point.

In contrast to the FTL approach, where fault trees are typically large and offer few variations, ETL approach fault trees are usually small but contain distinct components not found in any other logic model within the accident sequence. Accident sequence frequency is determined by multiplying the conditional split fractions for the sequence. Due to the small size of the top event logic models in ETL, different analysts generally construct similar models. However, variations may occur in the structure of equivalent event trees constructed by different analysts.

1.5 Multi-Hazard PRA Models

1.5.1 Overview of Multi-Hazard PRA Models

Concurrent and successive occurrences of more than one hazard are defined as multi-hazard [43]. In the nuclear industry, multi-hazards are often overlooked in PRA since no general framework is available for such an analysis.

Multi-hazard PRA became a topic after the Fukushima NPP accident in March 2011. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) [44], the Great East Japan Earthquake was a 9.0-magnitude earthquake followed by a tsunami on the eastern coast. According to the International Nuclear Event Scale (INES) [45], this event, caused by a multi-hazard, led to a level 7 accident at Fukushima Daiichi NPP, the highest level, according to the International Nuclear Event Scale (INES). While the Three Mile Island accident in the US made PRA crucial, the Fukushima Daiichi accident showed the necessity for multi-hazard PRA.

Multi-hazard PRA is a more complex analysis, and assessing its necessity is more challenging than the single-hazard analysis [46]. As discussed above, the accidents made the PRA crucial for NPP; climate change and the growing population increased the frequency of local, regional, or global hazards. This increase may lead to a higher impact on critical infrastructures, such as NPP, than anticipated when they were designed.

Besides single-hazard analysis, multi-hazard PRA requires different analysis methods since every hazard has characteristics [47]. Therefore, to better understand and find ways to quantify multi-hazard PRA, a feasible approach could be to categorize the multi-hazards and define standard parameters.

Although there is more than one way to categorize the multi-hazards, in this paper, we prefer to walk through the categorization given in Table 1 [48], which suggests the order of events is also important to classify the events besides the number of events.

Table 1. Multi-hazard categorization

Categories		Details
Number of events and hazards	Number of events	Single event: one event and one hazard Multi-event: two or more events, including a secondary event
	Number of hazards	Single hazard: one hazard (it may be caused even by multi-event) Multi-hazard: two or more hazards (it may be caused even by a single event)
Order of event	Independent event [Independent]	Two or more events that are independent of each other
	Simultaneous event [Concurrent]	Two or more events caused by a single source
	Sequential event [Successive]	Occurred by secondary event

Multiple definitions for multi-hazard PRA can be found in the literature; thus, providing descriptive definitions is necessary to understand Table 1:

- *Hazards* are phenomena that challenge the safe operation of an NPP, such as seismic or high wind.
- *Hazard event* is an event caused by the occurrence of the specified hazard described in terms of various levels of some characteristic measure of its intensity, such as the peak ground acceleration for seismic hazards or wind speed for high wind hazards.
- *Initiating events* cover natural and human-made perturbations to the plant that can challenge control and safety systems whose failure can lead to undesired consequences, such as radioactive material release. An initiating event can result from various hazard events internal (e.g., hardware fault, flood, fire) or external to the plant (e.g., earthquakes, high winds).
- *Hazard analysis* is estimating the expected frequency of exceedance over a specified time interval of various levels of some characteristic measure of the intensity of the hazard, such as water level in flood.
- *Secondary hazard* is a hazard induced by another hazard, like a landslide caused by an earthquake.
- *Multi-hazard* is a phenomenon in which one hazard occurs concurrently with another hazard, like seismic and flooding.
- *Multi-hazard (initiating) event* is the occurrence of two or more correlated or uncorrelated events, like an earthquake of a specific peak group acceleration and high winds of a specific wind speed.

Although some definitions are not standard and highlight the need for a common language in multi-hazard PRA, the relationship between hazards, which may make analysis trivial or complex, must be considered in any approach.

In multi-hazard PRA, both internal and external events need to be addressed. External events are the events that occur outside the NPP. The external events' hazards may be the natural environment or man-made ones. However, multi-hazard PRA is not only related to external events but also related to internal events. For example, a large break loss of cooling (LBLOCA) initiating event can happen during an earthquake [49].

A well-known example is the Fukushima Daiichi NPP accident, an internal accident induced by an external earthquake and tsunami. The lesson learned from this accident is that the PRA for external events, combined events, and external hazards causing internal events needs to be revised. Therefore, there is a need to develop a framework that considers the combination of external events by considering the likelihood of the risk contributors and their effects.

In general, hazard events can occur individually or in combination. Two combined hazard events occur simultaneously or within a short duration. Moreover, they may also cause an internal event, such as equipment failure. This simple illustration is just like the accident of Fukushima Daiichi NPP. The takeout from this example is that considering the different events as independent may not always be a reasonable assumption. Such simplification ignores the correlation between events and may lead to unintended consequences.

Identifying individual hazards depends on screening analysis, established to collect information on plant characteristics concerning internal and external hazards, statistical methods, and experiences investigating hazards and their impacts on the plant [50].

Any hazards can be treated in four steps [51]:

- Initial data collection can be either site- or plant-specific. Then, the data is the source for screening analysis.
- Identification of hazards is the next step in data gathering. The source of the hazards may be either natural or man-made.
- Hazard screening analysis aims to screen out insignificant items or items with insignificant effects.
- Detailed hazards analysis analyzes the relevant hazards affecting structures, systems, or components (SSCs).

The current practice considers two or more hazard events as independent events and evaluates the total frequency as the product of single frequencies. It is straightforward and makes evaluation extremely easy; however, this is not always appropriate.

The studies on multi-hazard PRA in nuclear are not mature yet; however, a couple of efforts are ongoing. NARSIS [52] aims to review, analyze, and improve the safety assessment methodologies. A practical approach was presented for performing an earthquake-induced landslide PRA for NPP [53]. Another study [54] demonstrated the results from a survey of multi-hazard PRA that was conducted using a Bayesian Network (BN) with Bayesian inference. One comparatively older study [55] developed a systematic methodology to assess and rank the risk from multiple hazards in a community. The final example study [56] describes NRC's Office of Nuclear Regulatory Research's initial efforts to support a portion of the Level 3 project: the multi-hazard Level-2 PRA for LWRs.

1.5.2 Multi-Hazard PRA Model Quantification

Multi-hazard PRA quantification is crucial because using approximation methods to calculate probabilities can introduce significant errors compared to exact failure probability calculations. However, exact calculation using BDD is often not feasible due to the high memory requirements. On the other hand, high basic event failure probabilities tend to lead to overestimated top event failure probabilities when using approximation methods like MCUB and REA. To address this issue, we propose a quantification engine-agnostic model pre-processor.

```

1. Parse given input files
2. Gather all failure probabilities for basic events
3. Create a dictionary for each input file as a key, failure probabilities as a value
4. Set threshold for a basic event failure probability value
5. Count how many failure probabilities are less than the predetermined threshold value
6. If more than the predefined percentage of failure probabilities is less than the predetermined threshold value
7. Then, solve the model using `mocus mcub`
8. Else solve model using `bdd`

```

Figure 8. Pseudocode for proposed PRA model pre-processor.

As illustrated in Figure 8, the proposed pre-processor operates by evaluating all input text files independently and directing solvers to either use the *mocus mcub* method or the *bdd* method. This approach enables exact quantification for models with high failure probabilities while allowing for approximate quantification for models with lower failure probabilities. In the following report, a predetermined threshold, based on a predefined percentage of failure probabilities, will be established and demonstrated.

1.6 Benchmarking, and Profiling of Quantification Engines - A Framework with a Case Study

This section outlines a framework for systematically benchmarking and profiling a PRA tool called diagnostic methodology, as illustrated in Figure 9, which is an apt analogy for our approach to improving PRA tools. As individuals seek medical attention when they

feel unwell, our methodology involves identifying and addressing issues within the PRA tool.

Figure 9. Overview of diagnostic methodology for a PRA tool.

Firstly, researchers conduct quick diagnostics akin to a doctor's initial assessment, using benchmarking to measure the tool's CPU time and memory usage performance. However, benchmarking alone may not reveal the underlying issues, so further investigation is necessary.

Profiling the code allows researchers to delve deeper and pinpoint any bottlenecks or inefficiencies, providing crucial insights for improvement decisions. These improvements may involve modifying the source code or leveraging parallel computing to enhance performance.

Before releasing the updated version of the PRA tool, rigorous testing using test models is essential to ensure correctness and reliability. Once the improvements are approved and validated, the updated tool can be made available to users, empowering them with enhanced functionality and efficiency.

Section 1.6.1 introduces a comparative analysis and performance evaluation methodology termed *quick diagnostic* for the PRA tool. This approach offers insights into the tool's performance under specific conditions and within a defined timeframe. However, a thorough examination of the source code is necessary for a more comprehensive understanding and to establish an enhancement roadmap. A thorough examination of the source code is necessary to gain a deeper understanding and establish an enhancement roadmap involving identifying areas needing updates. This

more detailed approach, termed *profiling*, as elaborated in Section 1.6.2, is referred to as *detailed diagnostics*.

An enhancement roadmap is developed through the combined outcomes of quick and detailed diagnostics. This roadmap may include code optimization and the utilization of parallel computing, among other strategies, to optimize the performance of PRA tools.

The methodology provided here can be applied to all PRA tools with minimal effort.

1.6.1 Overview of Benchmarking

Benchmarking is a well-established computer science method primarily used to compare various methods, techniques, and tools [57].

In the dedicated benchmarking phase of our diagnostics methodology, three key inputs come into play: the PRA model, the PRA tool itself, and the benchmarking configuration, as depicted in Figure 10.

The generation of the PRA model is intricately tied to the specific PRA tool under analysis. For benchmarking purposes, only the executable version of the PRA tool is required.

Configuration plays a pivotal role in benchmarking by establishing parameters and constraints. These configurations are essential for ensuring consistency and relevance across various runs.

The configuration of benchmarking is critical for replicating the work and defining the limits of each run in advance. By controlling all runs with predetermined limits, configuration ensures that the performance of the PRA tool is evaluated under standardized conditions tailored to the given computational environment.

Figure 10. Benchmarking methodology for a PRA tool.

Once these three ingredients are ready, the benchmarking process begins, measuring CPU time and memory usage for each model run. These metrics provide valuable insights into the performance and resource utilization of the PRA tool under various conditions, laying the groundwork for further analysis and improvement efforts.

Selecting the benchmarking environment is crucial, and one approach is to integrate timers directly into the source code, provided it is accessible. However, it is essential to consider that the measured time may be influenced by other concurrent processes running on the computer. All other concurrent processes should be excluded from the benchmarking run to ensure accurate and efficient measurement of performance metrics. This ensures that the benchmarking environment remains isolated and focused on accurately capturing the performance of the PRA tool. We prefer Benchexec [58], an open-source framework for reliable benchmarking [89], and resource management to address the benchmarking requirements mentioned.

1.6.2 Overview of Standard Profiling

The profiling methodology, illustrated in Figure 11, involves using a challenging PRA model to better understand the source code by allowing sufficient runtime.

This model, selected from benchmarking results, serves as a comprehensive test for the PRA tool. Preparing the PRA tool involves compiling it in release mode with the highest compiler optimization level and generating debug information for accurate profiling.

Figure 11. Profiling methodology for a PRA tool.

Once the model and PRA tool are ready, the next step is to set up the profiler. Profilers are classified into four categories [60, p. 586]: text-based, high-level, medium-level, and detailed profilers. Each category offers different levels of insight into application performance. For this study, VTune [61] was chosen as it provides comprehensive and detailed information while also offering a user-friendly graphical interface. Despite not capturing every nuance of the PRA tool's performance, VTune's accessibility and comprehensive profiling capabilities make it a suitable choice for this research. Also, VTune is compatible with all operating systems.

VTune profiling begins with an overall code performance analysis, identifying areas that require further assessment, such as hot spot analysis.

1.6.3 Case Study

The methodology has been demonstrated using various tools, and the results have been presented at conferences [1], [62]. Below is an application of the methodology to SCRAM and SAPHSOLVE.

1.6.3.1 Benchmarking of SCRAM and SAPHSOLVE

a. Model Generation

The key to generating models for quantification engines lies in creating identical models for accurate comparisons. However, when applying the provided methodology, users may encounter unfamiliarity with the specific PRA tool. Synthetic models are utilized for the case study to address this challenge and gain insights into complex sources. Synthetic models offer flexibility in identifying complexity origins and assessing the impact on resource consumption during quantification.

Table 2. PRA model generator arguments with case study configurations.

#	Argument	Options	Configurations
1	Name for fault tree	--ft-name	Autogenerated
2	Name for the root gate	--root	Root
3	Seed for PRNG	--seed	123
4	Number of basic events	--num-basic	100:50:5000
5	Average number of gate arguments	-num-args	3.0
6	Weights for gates [AND, OR, K/N, NOT, XOR]	--weights-g	[1,1,1,0,0]
7	Average percentage of common basic events per gate	--common-b	0.3
8	Average percentage of common gates per gate	--common-g	0.1
9	Average number of parents for common basic events	--parents-b	2
10	Average number of parents for common basic events	--parents-g	2
11	Number of gates	-g or -num-gate	0
12	Maximum probability of basic events	---max-prob	0.05
13	Minimum probability of basic events	--min-prob	0.01
14	Number of house events	--num-house	0
15	Number of common-cause-failure groups	--num-ccf	0
16	A file to write the fault tree	-o or -out	XML or JSInp
17	Apply the other format to the output	--other	--saphsolve

These synthetic models are generated using a fault tree generator, relying on seventeen essential parameters outlined in Table 2. Careful configuration of fault trees, as specified in the fourth column, ensures diverse models are constructed. The number of basic

events is systematically adjusted, ranging from 100 to 5,000 with 50-event increments, resulting in 99 models for each engine. Each gate within the fault trees—whether an *AND*, *OR*, or *K/N* gate—is randomly selected, with each gate type's average occurrence expected to match one another closely.

The configuration also considers common basic events, with probabilities chosen judiciously to strike a balance between avoiding values that trigger premature truncation and steering apparent of overly large values that contravene the rare-event approximation.

It is important to note a significant modeling difference between SCRAM and SAPHSOLVE: SCRAM accepts truncation parameters or values via the command line, whereas SAPHSOLVE accepts them inside the input file. A probability truncation value of 10^{-20} is used, while no size truncation is applied for either tool.

Additionally, common cause failures, uncertainty analysis, and importance measurement are intentionally excluded from this study and reserved for future work.

The SAPHSOLVE [34] and SCRAM [63] models utilized for this work are accessible through the repositories.

b. Configurations

The configuration process begins with successfully installing Benchexec in the testing environment. Following installation, SCRAM and SAPHSOLVE are defined as tools to be recognized by Benchexec. This involves defining the tools in a Python script, as outlined in the Benchexec manual, which allows for the execution of the tools via the command line and retrieval of the resulting data. SCRAM and SAPHSOLVE tool files are illustrated in Figure 12 and Figure 13, respectively.

```
1. '''
2. This file includes tool information required by Benchexec.
3. To benchmark SCRAM, this file should be placed in the path of
4. "/home/user/.local/lib/python3.10/site-packages/benchexec/tools"
5. '''
6.
7. import benchexec.result as result
8. import benchexec.tools.template
9.
10. class Tool(benchexec.tools.template.BaseTool2):
11.     def executable(self, tool_locator):
12.         return tool_locator.find_executable("scram")
13.
14.     def name(self):
15.         return "SCRAM"
16.
17.     def version(self, executable):
18.         return self._version_from_tool(executable)
19.
20.     def cmdline(self, executable, options, task, rlimits):
21.         cmd = [executable] + options
22.         if task.property_file:
23.             cmd.append(task.property_file)
24.         return cmd + list(task.input_files)
25.
26.     def determine_result(self, run):
27.         status = result.RESULT_ERROR
28.         if run.output.any_line_contains("results"):
29.             status = result.RESULT_DONE
30.         if run.output.any_line_contains("warning"):
31.             status = result.RESULT_UNKNOWN
32.         return status
```

Figure 12. SCRAM Python script as Benchexec tool.

```

1. '''
2. This file includes tool information required by Benchexec.
3. To benchmark SAPH SOLVE, this file should be placed in the path of
4. "/home/user/.local/lib/python3.10/site-packages/benchexec/tools"
5. '''
6.
7. import benchexec.result as result
8. import benchexec.tools.template
9.
10. class Tool(benchexec.tools.template.BaseTool2):
11.     def executable(self, tool_locator):
12.         return tool_locator.find_executable("saphsolve")
13.
14.     def name(self):
15.         return "SAPH SOLVE"
16.
17.     def version(self, executable):
18.         return self._version_from_tool(executable)
19.
20.     def cmdline(self, executable, options, task, rlimits):
21.         cmd = [executable]
22.         if task.property_file:
23.             cmd.append(task.property_file)
24.         options = list(filter(None, options))
25.         cmd = cmd + list(task.input_files) + options
26.         return cmd
27.
28.     def determine_result(self, run):
29.         status = result.RESULT_UNKNOWN
30.         return status

```

Figure 13. SAPH SOLVE Python script as Benchexec tool.

For the case study, a benchmarking configuration is proposed, which includes a 30-minute time limit, 16 GB memory allocation, 1 CPU core, and 1 thread. These parameters establish a standardized environment for benchmarking the performance of the PRA tools. The configuration is defined using an XML file, as detailed in the Benchexec manual. Figure 14 and Figure 15 depict the XML configuration files for SCRAM and SAPH SOLVE, respectively. In these configuration files, not only are limitations specified, but run configurations are also defined along with the addresses of input models.

The benchmarking for this study was conducted on a Dell Inc. OptiFlex 7060 machine equipped with 16 GiB of memory. The system features an Intel Core i7-8700 CPU clocked at 3.20 GHz with 12 processors [64]. Additionally, it boasts a capacious 2.0 TB disk capacity and operates on a 64-bit Ubuntu 22.04.2 LTS operating system.

```

1. <!DOCTYPE benchmark PUBLIC "+//IDN sosalab.org//DTD BenchExec benchmark 2.3//EN" "https://www.sosalab.org/benchexec/benchmark-2.2.3dtd">
2. <benchmark tool="scram"
3.     timelimit="30min"
4.     memlimit="16 GB"
5.     cpuCores="1"
6.     threads="1">
7.     <option name="--probability" />
8.     <option name="--cut-off">1e-20</option>
9.
10.
11. <rundefinition name="scram.mocus.trunc.mcub.no-limit">
12.     <option name="--mocus" />
13.     <option name="--mcub" />
14. </rundefinition>
15.
16. <rundefinition name="scram.mocus.trunc.rare-event.no-limit">
17.     <option name="--mocus" />
18.     <option name="--rare-event" />
19. </rundefinition>
20.
21. <rundefinition name="scram.bdd.no-limit">
22.     <option name="--bdd" />
23. </rundefinition>
24.
25. <rundefinition name="scram.zbdd.no-limit">
26.     <option name="--zbdd" />
27. </rundefinition>
28.
29. <tasks name="combined-and-or-k-n-without-ccf">
30.     <includesfile>/home/egemen-ubuntu/benchmarking/scram/input-openpsa/scram.txt</includesfile>
31. </tasks>
32. </benchmark>

```

Figure 14. SCRAM configuration file.

```

1. <!DOCTYPE benchmark PUBLIC "+//IDN sosalab.org//DTD BenchExec benchmark 2.3//EN" "https://www.sosalab.org/benchexec/benchmark-2.2.3dtd">
2. <benchmark tool="saphsolve"
3.     timelimit="30min"
4.     memlimit="16 GB"
5.     cpuCores="1"
6.     threads="1">
7.     <option name="">/dev/fd/1</option>
8.     <rundefinition name="saphsolve">
9.     </rundefinition>
10.
11. <tasks name="saphsolve.mocus.trunc.mcub.no-limit">
12.     <includesfile>/home/egemen-ubuntu/benchmarking/saphsolve/input-
jsinp/saphsolve.txt</includesfile>
13. </tasks>
14. </benchmark>

```

Figure 15. SAPH SOLVE configuration file.

c. Results and Discussions

In the quick diagnostics phase, the benchmarking results of SCRAM and SAPH SOLVE are analyzed to assess various performance metrics, including CPU time, memory usage, the number of cut sets generated, and probability calculation. SCRAM offers three options for generating cut sets: MOCUS, BDD, and ZBDD, along with two options for probability calculation: MCUB and REA. In contrast, SAPH SOLVE employs the MOCUS algorithm for cut set generation and MCUB for probability calculation. As a result, SCRAM provides more detailed results due to its multiple options.

Each set of results is individually examined to understand the performance characteristics of each quantification engine. Additionally, comparisons are made between the number of cut sets generated and the probability results obtained by each engine. This comparative analysis sheds light on any differences or similarities in performance between SCRAM and SAPH SOLVE, providing valuable insights into their efficiency and effectiveness in PRA model quantification.

Starting with SCRAM, Table 3 briefly summarises the results obtained from running 99 input files. Regrettably, only 3 exact results were obtained from SCRAM-BDD. However, the MOCUS algorithm and ZBDD algorithm, along with probability approximation, were successful in quantifying almost all models.

Table 3. Number of quantified input files for each run.

Quantification Engine- Approach- Approximation	SCRAM- MOCUS - MCUB	SCRAM- MOCUS- REA	SCRAM- BDD	SCRAM- ZBDD- REA	SAPH SOLVE- MOCUS-MCUB
Number of Quantified Input File	89	89	3	90	82

The models that cannot be quantified are also analyzed, revealing that the calculation halts during SCRAM's cut set generation step. For illustrative purposes, one of the unresolved models, ft-1300, is selected, and its quantification is attempted by adjusting the limit order in the size of MCS. The analysis reveals an exponential relationship between the limit order of MCS and the quantification time, as illustrated in Figure 16.

Figure 16. The effect of limit order on MCS of SCRAM for ft-1300 model.

Notably, 85 of the models yielded the same number of cut sets when quantified using either MOCUS or ZBDD. In a few cases, ZBDD and MOCUS produced different results for quantifying specific models. As expected, the ZBDD approach utilized the REA approximation for probability calculation.

Comparing SCRAM-MOCUS-MCUB and SAPHSSOLVE-MOCUS-MCUB, it is notable that the probability results are identical, serving as a valuable cross-check of these two distinct engines.

As illustrated in Figure 17, the quantification time of SCRAM appears to be approximately linear with the number of cut sets generated. While most models were generated within the given time limit, there were instances where certain models took up to 20 minutes to quantify. This extended duration is not deemed acceptable for a PRA model, especially considering that the models in the benchmarking study only consist of a fault tree. In actual NPP models, which may contain several event trees linked with multiple fault trees, such delays would be even less tolerable.

Another notable finding is that BDD is the fastest method if sufficient resources are available. Additionally, it is worth mentioning that the ZBDD approach is significantly faster than the MOCUS algorithm. This observation suggests that future improvements

may substantially reduce quantification uncertainty, even with the same computer resources available.

Figure 17. SCRAM quantification time results for all approaches available.

Figure 18. SCRAM memory usage for all approaches available.

The memory usage of SCRAM, as depicted in Figure 18, is notable. Excluding several small models, there is a noticeable increase in memory requirements for all quantified models. A significant outcome is that BDD runs are not feasible due to the high memory demands. Conversely, the flat line in the figure represents our predefined limit. Memory usage is expected to increase if we allocate more memory resources.

When examining the SAPH SOLVE results, it quantifies 82 out of 99 models using the MOCUS approach with MCUB probability approximation. We observe superb performance from SAPH SOLVE, as depicted in Figure 19, with each quantification taking only milliseconds with the predefined truncation in probability. However, it is essential to note a crucial limitation: the Linux version of SAPH SOLVE is not as capable as the Windows version when running without truncation.

Figure 19. SAPH SOLVE quantification time results for MOCUS MCUB.

On the positive side, SAPH SOLVE is relatively fast because it stops immediately and does not report as many cut sets as SCRAM. The reason for this is that it has been identified that SCRAM reports all cut sets without considering the truncation probability. Additionally, with the given configurations, the probability calculation results are the same as those obtained with SCRAM MCUB. Another notable aspect where SAPH SOLVE excels is in its output; unlike SCRAM, SAPH SOLVE does not provide any detailed output. This difference contributes to SAPH SOLVE's speed, as it only dumps minimal information

to a JSON file compared to SCRAM, which writes out a significant amount of information to an XML file.

Figure 20. SAPHSOLVE memory usage for MOCUS MCUB.

SAPHSOLVE's memory usage is also remarkably efficient, as depicted in Figure 20. However, it is essential to note that the number of cut sets stored is significantly lower than that of SCRAM. For example, while SCRAM produces 10^7 cut sets, SAPHSOLVE generates 10^5 . This significant difference translates into faster results due to efficient resource management.

The results suggest that various strategies and implementations can lead to bottlenecks or efficient resource management. It is crucial to justify each truncation and approximation before sacrificing accuracy. Additionally, while benchmarking results highlight bottlenecks, they do not directly address improvements. Further analysis is required before developing a detailed improvement plan.

d. Conclusion

The benchmarking step serves as a crucial mechanism for assessing the performance of PRA tools. Additionally, it establishes a verification environment for both code and solution, not only for SAPHSOLVE and SCRAM but also for all PRA tools.

1.6.3.2 Standard Profiling of SCRAM and SAPHSOLVE

a. Preparations & Configuration

While both tools are quantification engines, they differ in several aspects. SCRAM is compatible with Open-PSA MEF, whereas SAPHSOLVE has its own model format. Additionally, SCRAM is written in C++, while SAPHSOLVE is written in Delphi. For SAPHSOLVE, a conversion tool called map2pdb [65] is required to transform the MAP files generated by Delphi compilers into Microsoft PDB files, which are vital components for utilization within VTune. Once the necessary MAP files are generated, the SAPHSOLVE engine becomes primed for profiling via VTune.

As benchmarking results will inform the profiling step, no specific limitations are defined for the profiling process. This allows for a comprehensive analysis of the PRA tools' performance without constraints on resource usage during profiling.

It is worth noting that while benchmarking requires a consistent environment for fair comparison between quantification engines, the profiling step does not necessitate the same environment since its focus is on exploring the source code to identify performance bottlenecks.

For SCRAM profiling, the same computer resources are used, along with a selected fault tree that includes 450 basic events (ft-450 model) for MOCUS MCUB, MOCUS REA, ZBDD, and 350 basic events (ft-350 model) for BDD, using the same configuration as in the benchmarking study. Since we are delving into the source code, the computer environment and PRA models do not necessarily need to be identical for different quantification engines.

For SAPHSOLVE profiling analysis, a fault tree including 310 basic events (ft-310 model), with the same configuration as in the benchmarking study, is used. However, the environment for SAPHSOLVE is different now, as it has switched from a Linux to a Windows 10 environment with an Intel 2.3 GHz CPU. This change was motivated by a significant finding from the benchmarking study, which revealed notable differences between the Linux and Windows versions of SAPHSOLVE. The Windows version outperforms and is capable of handling size truncation.

b. Results and Discussions

In detailed diagnostics, each quantification engine undergoes a thorough analysis to identify specific areas of inefficiency or bottlenecks within the source code, often referred to as *hot spots*.

Once hot spots are identified, developers can prioritize these areas for optimization based on their impact on overall performance. Common strategies for addressing hot spots may

include code refactoring, algorithmic optimizations, parallelization techniques, or the utilization of more efficient data structures.

Overall, detailed diagnostics play a crucial role in the optimization process by providing actionable insights into the inner workings of the quantification engines, ultimately leading to enhanced performance and efficiency.

The performance analysis results and the given input file are presented in Table 4 for SCRAM and Table 5 for SAPHSOLVE.

Table 4. Summary of profiling performance analysis results for SCRAM

Quantification Engine- Approach-Approximation	SCRAM- MOCUS - MCUB	SCRAM- MOCUS- REA	SCRAM- BDD	SCRAM- ZBDD- REA
Input File Configuration	ft-450	ft-450	ft-350	ft-450
Analysis Elapsed Time [sec]	431.230	426.177	62.566	320.072
Physical Core Utilization	0.972 out of 6			

It is observed that neither of the codes can be used in parallel execution. However, these tables provide insights beyond that. The following analysis delves into the hot spot analysis for each case.

Table 5. Summary of profiling performance analysis results for SAPHSOLVE

Truncation Size	16	18	20
Input File Configuration	ft-310	ft-310	ft-310
Analysis Elapsed Time [sec]	361.010	4,142.099	64,365.847
Number of Cut Sets	11,490	102,444	761,472
Probability	1.3388x10 ⁻¹¹		
Physical Core Utilization	1.306 out of 4		

Table 5 provides a more detailed comparison than Table 4, especially considering the Windows environment, which allows for a better comparison of the engines in terms of size truncation. As investigated in the benchmarking section, the SAPHSOLVE Linux version demonstrates considerable speed and efficiency in memory management. However, when SAPHSOLVE encounters larger truncation values, like SCRAM, its performance undergoes significant changes and becomes significantly slower, mainly when the truncation size is between 16 and 20. To compare the results, SCRAM and SAPHSOLVE yield the same number of cut sets for a truncation size of 20. An initial finding from the profiling analysis suggests that the SAPHSOLVE engine may need to

revisit its size truncation implementation, as it significantly slows down the calculation process.

To elaborate further, the relationship between truncation size and calculation time exhibits an exponential trend in SAPHSOLVE, as illustrated in Figure 21.

Figure 21. SAPHSOLVE quantification time for different truncation sizes.

Analysis Configuration		Collection Log	Summary	Bottom-up	Caller/Callee	Top-down Tree	Flame Graph	Platform
Grouping: Call Stack								
Function Stack								CPU Time: Total
▼ Total								100.0%
▼ _start								100.0%
▼ _libc_start_main_impl								100.0%
▼ main								100.0%
▼ RunScram								100.0%
▶ scram::Reporter::Report								73.3%
▼ scram::core::RiskAnalysis::Analyze								26.6%
▼ scram::core::RiskAnalysis::RunAnalysis								26.6%
▼ scram::core::RiskAnalysis::RunAnalysis<scram::core::Mocus>								26.6%
▼ scram::core::FaultTreeAnalysis::Analyze								22.7%
▶ scram::core::FaultTreeAnalyzer<scram::core::Mocus>::GenerateProducts								18.2%
▶ scram::core::FaultTreeAnalysis::Store								4.5%
▶ scram::core::FaultTreeAnalyzer<scram::core::Mocus>::Preprocess								0.0%
▶ scram::core::RiskAnalysis::RunAnalysis<scram::core::Mocus, scram::core::McubCalculator>								4.0%
▶ scram::mef::Initializer::Initializer								0.0%

Figure 22. SCRAM MOCUS MCUB Vtune profiling results.

In the SCRAM hot spot analysis, it is observed that reporting results and cut set generation consume most of the computation time for the MOCUS and ZBDD algorithms. Conversely, BDD construction accounts for almost all the computation time for the BDD

algorithm. As illustrated in Figure 22 and Figure 23, the results for MOCUS MCUB and MOCUS REA are similar, except for the probability calculation step. As expected, MCUB probability calculation takes slightly longer than REA since it considers more terms.

Function Stack	CPU Time: Total
▼ Total	100.0%
▼ _start	100.0%
▼ __libc_start_main_impl	100.0%
▼ main	100.0%
▼ RunScram	100.0%
▶ scram::Reporter::Report	74.2%
▼ scram::core::RiskAnalysis::Analyze	25.8%
▼ scram::core::RiskAnalysis::RunAnalysis	25.8%
▼ scram::core::RiskAnalysis::RunAnalysis<scram::core::Mocus>	25.8%
▼ scram::core::FaultTreeAnalysis::Analyze	22.0%
▶ scram::core::FaultTreeAnalyzer<scram::core::Mocus>::GenerateProducts	17.7%
▶ scram::core::FaultTreeAnalysis::Store	4.3%
▶ scram::core::FaultTreeAnalyzer<scram::core::Mocus>::Preprocess	0.0%
▶ scram::core::RiskAnalysis::RunAnalysis<scram::core::Mocus, scram::core::RareEventCalculator>	3.8%
▶ scram::mef::Initializer::Initializer	0.0%

Figure 23. SCRAM MOCUS REA Vtune profiling results.

Figure 24 suggests that BDD construction requires an update. BDD construction is a non-trivial step, and while various methods are available, current BDD packages are not yet capable of supporting actual NPP PRA models.

Function Stack	CPU Time: Total
▼ Total	100.0%
▼ _start	100.0%
▼ __libc_start_main_impl	100.0%
▼ main	100.0%
▼ RunScram	100.0%
▼ scram::core::RiskAnalysis::Analyze	99.0%
▼ scram::core::RiskAnalysis::RunAnalysis	99.0%
▶ scram::core::RiskAnalysis::RunAnalysis<scram::core::Bdd>	99.0%
▶ scram::core::RiskAnalysis::~RiskAnalysis	0.8%
▶ scram::Reporter::Report	0.1%
▶ scram::mef::Initializer::Initializer	0.1%

Figure 24. SCRAM BDD Vtune profiling results.

SCRAM's ZBDD approach automatically utilizes REA to calculate failure probabilities, as shown in Figure 25. ZBDD construction is notably fast compared to BDD construction, making it a promising approach for generating cut sets efficiently and quickly.

Analysis Configuration		Collection Log	Summary	Bottom-up	Caller/Callee	Top-down Tree	Flame Graph	Platform
Grouping: Call Stack								
Function Stack								CPU Time: Total
▼ Total								100.0%
▼ _start								100.0%
▼ __libc_start_main_impl								100.0%
▼ main								100.0%
▼ RunScram								100.0%
▶ scram::Reporter::Report								94.1%
▼ scram::core::RiskAnalysis::Analyze								5.8%
▼ scram::core::RiskAnalysis::RunAnalysis								5.8%
▼ scram::core::RiskAnalysis::RunAnalysis<scram::core::Zbdd>								5.8%
▶ scram::core::FaultTreeAnalysis::Analyze								3.7%
▶ scram::core::RiskAnalysis::RunAnalysis<scram::core::Zbdd, scram::core::RareEventCalculator>								2.1%
▶ scram::mef::Initializer::Initializer								0.0%

Figure 25. SCRAM ZBDD REA Vtune profiling results.

Hot spots are also identified in SAPH SOLVE for each truncation size, as given in Table 6. The functions are masked to avoid confusion with assigned names. It is discovered that functions A and B dominate the entire run for all truncation sizes. As the truncation size increases, the contribution of function B to the overall runtime significantly rises, exceeding 70%. These functions are responsible for generating cut sets.

Table 6. SAPH SOLVE MOCUS MCUB Vtune profiling results.

Truncation Size	Function	CPU Time [sec]	Percentage Contribution to Whole Run [%]
16	A	175.643	49.5
	B	52.284	14.7
18	B	1648.13	43
	A	708.83	18.5
20	B	43893.54	72.2
	C	3929.234	6.5
	A	3580.815	5.9

c. Conclusion

Standard profiling facilitates detailed diagnostics of the PRA tool, pinpointing areas needing improvement. It remains applicable to all PRA tools as long as their source code is accessible.

1.7 Conclusion and Alignment to Project Goals

The successful completion of the project relies on a well-established literature review and the development of a robust framework for benchmarking and profiling PRA tools. A

comprehensive review of PRA tools, including current issues, PRA model structures, and model quantification, was conducted. A framework for benchmarking and profiling was also developed, and two quantifications were tested using this framework. The framework also facilitates the generation of synthetic models for testing purposes. Furthermore, it serves as a verification environment between different quantification engines. These achievements, along with the case study results, will contribute to the subsequent tasks of the project.

Additionally, a quantification engine-agnostic model pre-processor is proposed to efficiently quantify multi-hazard models, optimizing the process based on the available computing resources. The demonstration of this pre-processor will be presented in subsequent reports.

2 References

- [1] E. M. Aras, A. S. Farag, A. Earthperson, and M. A. Diaconeasa, "Benchmark Study of XFTA and SCRAM Fault Tree Solvers Using Synthetically Generated Fault Trees Models," in *Volume 9: Mechanics of Solids, Structures, and Fluids; Micro- and Nano-Systems Engineering and Packaging; Safety Engineering, Risk, and Reliability Analysis; Research Posters*, Columbus, Ohio, USA: American Society of Mechanical Engineers, Oct. 2022, p. V009T14A016. doi: 10.1115/IMECE2022-95783.
- [2] E. M. Aras, A. S. Farag, A. Earthperson, and M. A. Diaconeasa, "Methodology and Demonstration for Performance Analysis of a Probabilistic Risk Assessment Quantification Engine: SCRAM," in *18th International Probabilistic Safety Assessment and Analysis (PSA 2023)*, Knoxville, TN: American Nuclear Society, 2023, pp. 452–459.
- [3] E. M. Aras, A. S. Farag, A. Earthperson, and M. A. Diaconeasa, "Method of Developing a SCRAM Parallel Engine for Efficient Quantification of Probabilistic Risk Assessment Models," in *18th International Probabilistic Safety Assessment and Analysis (PSA 2023)*, Knoxville, TN: American Nuclear Society, 2023, pp. 134–140.
- [4] A. Earthperson, E. M. Aras, A. S. Farag, and M. A. Diaconeasa, "Introducing OpenPRA: A Web-Based Framework for Collaborative Probabilistic Risk Assessment," in *Proceedings of the ASME 2023*, New Orleans, Louisiana, USA, Oct. 2023.
- [5] A. Farag, S. Wood, A. Earthperson, E. Aras, J. Boyce, and M. Diaconeasa, "Evaluating PRA Tools for Accurate and Efficient Quantifications: A Follow-Up Benchmarking Study Including FTREX," in *Advanced Reactor Safety (ARS)*, Las Vegas, NV: American Nuclear Society, 2024, pp. 573–582. doi: 10.13182/T130-43377.
- [6] E. Aras *et al.*, "Introducing OpenPRA's Quantification Engine: Exploring Capabilities, Recognizing Limitations, and Charting the Path to Enhancement," in *Advanced Reactor Safety (ARS)*, Las Vegas, NV: American Nuclear Society, 2024, pp. 552–561. doi: 10.13182/T130-43362.
- [7] E. Aras, S. Wood, J. Boyce, A. Farag, and M. Diaconeasa, "Enhancing the SAPHIRE Solve Engine: Initial Progress and Efforts," in *Advanced Reactor Safety (ARS)*, Las Vegas, NV: American Nuclear Society, 2024, pp. 542–551. doi: 10.13182/T130-43361.
- [8] S. Wood, J. Boyce, E. Aras, A. Farag, and M. Diaconeasa, "Advancing SAPHIRE: Transitioning from Legacy to State-of-Art Excellence," in *Advanced Reactor Safety (ARS)*, Las Vegas, NV: American Nuclear Society, 2024, pp. 532–541. doi: 10.13182/T130-43357.
- [9] A. Earthperson, E. Aras, A. Farag, and M. Diaconeasa, "Towards a Deep-Learning based Heuristic for Optimal Variable Ordering in Binary Decision Diagrams to Support Fault Tree Analysis," in *Advanced Reactor Safety (ARS)*, Las Vegas, NV: American Nuclear Society, 2024, pp. 400–409. doi: 10.13182/T130-43397.
- [10] E. M. Aras and M. A. Diaconeasa, "A Critical Look at the Need for Performing Multi-Hazard Probabilistic Risk Assessment for Nuclear Power Plants," *Eng*, vol. 2, pp. 454–467, 2021.

- [11] E. M. Aras, A. S. Amin Aly Farag, S. T. Wood, and J. T. Boyce, "Refining Processing Engines from SAPHIRE: Initialization of Fault Tree/Event Tree Solver," Idaho National Laboratory (INL), Idaho Falls, ID (United States), INL/RPT-23-75066-Rev000, Oct. 2023. doi: 10.2172/2203095.
- [12] A. S. Farag, "Benchmarking Study of Probabilistic Risk Assessment Tools Using Synthetically Generated Fault Tree Models: SAPHISOLVE, XFTA, and SCRAM," North Carolina State University, Raleigh, North Carolina, 2023.
- [13] E. M. Aras, "Enhancement Methodology for Probabilistic Risk Assessment Tools through Diagnostics, Optimization, and Parallel Computing," Doctor of Philosophy, North Carolina State University, Raleigh, North Carolina, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://repository.lib.ncsu.edu/items/bb05f7f5-1cff-4beb-9312-331bc94b0b95>
- [14] W. E. Vesely and R. E. Narum, "PREP and KITT Computer Codes for the Automatic Evaluation of a Fault Tree," Idaho Nuclear Corporation, Idaho, IN-1349, 1970.
- [15] J. B. Fussell, E. B. Henry, and N. H. Marshall, "MOCUS: a computer program to obtain minimal sets from fault trees," ANCR--1156, 4267950, Aug. 1974. doi: 10.2172/4267950.
- [16] S. Hoon Han, T. Woon Kim, and K. Joong Yoo, "Development of an integrated fault tree analysis computer code MODULE by modularization technique," *Reliab. Eng. Syst. Saf.*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 145–154, Jan. 1988, doi: 10.1016/0951-8320(88)90052-X.
- [17] L. L. N. Laboratory, "SIGPI:A USER'S MANUAL FOR FAST COMPUTATION OF THE PROBABILISTIC PERFORMANCE OF COMPLEX SYSTEMS.," p. 73.
- [18] J. M. Koren and J. Gaertner, *CAFTA: A fault tree analysis tool designed for PSA*. Germany: Verl TUEV Rheinland, 1987. [Online]. Available: http://inis.iaea.org/search/search.aspx?orig_q=RN:20061750
- [19] EPRI, "Phoenix Architect 2.0," Palo Alto, CA, 2021.
- [20] "NUREG/CR-7039, Vol. 1, 'Systems Analysis Programs for Hands-on Integrated Reliability Evaluations (SAPHIRE) Version 8, Volume 1: Overview and Summary.," 2011. doi: 10.2172/130641.
- [21] K. D. Russell and M. B. Sattison, "Living PRAs Made Easier With IRRAS," *Reliab. Eng. Syst. Saf.*, vol. 30, pp. 239–269, 1990.
- [22] K. D. Russell and D. M. Rasmuson, "Fault tree reduction and quantification—an overview of IRRAS algorithms," *Reliab. Eng. Syst. Saf.*, vol. 40, no. 2, pp. 149–164, Jan. 1993, doi: 10.1016/0951-8320(93)90105-8.
- [23] M. D. Wakefield, M. S. Epstein, D. Y. Xiong, and M. K. Nouri, "RISKMAN®, Celebrating 20+ Years of Excellence!," p. 10.
- [24] D. Wakefield, "Example Application of RISKMAN®," ABS Consulting, Inc., Operational Risk and Performance Consulting Division, 300 Commerce Drive 200, Irvine, CA, 92602, Sep. 2004. [Online]. Available: https://flightsafety.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/09/RISKMAN_application.pdf
- [25] S. H. Han, T. W. Kim, and K. S. Jeong, "PC Workstation-Based Level 1 PRA Code Package KIRAP," p. 10.
- [26] Manorma, "RiskSpectrum: Emerging software for Nuclear Power Industry," in *2010 1st International Nuclear & Renewable Energy Conference (INREC)*, Amman, Jordan: IEEE, Mar. 2010, pp. 1–6. doi: 10.1109/INREC.2010.5462562.

- [27] Y. Wu, "Development of reliability and probabilistic safety assessment program RiskA," *Ann. Nucl. Energy*, vol. 83, pp. 316–321, Sep. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.anucene.2015.03.020.
- [28] A. B. Rauzy, *Probabilistic Safety Analysis with XFTA*. ALTARICA ASSOCIATION, 2020.
- [29] O. Rakhimov, *SCRAM*. (Apr. 25, 2022). C++. Accessed: Apr. 25, 2022. [Online]. Available: 10.5281/zenodo.1146337
- [30] Z. Zhou, H. Nie, and Q. Zhang, "Design and Development of DeRisk: A Fault Tree Analysis Program Package," in *Volume 2: Plant Systems, Structures, Components, and Materials; Risk Assessments and Management*, London, England: American Society of Mechanical Engineers, Jul. 2018, p. V002T14A008. doi: 10.1115/ICONE26-81291.
- [31] A. Miller, S. Hess, and C. Smith, "R&D Roadmap to Enhance Industry Legacy Probabilistic Risk Assessment Methods and Tools," INL/EXT-20-59202, 2020.
- [32] E. Steven and R. Antoine, Eds., "Open-PSA Model Exchange Format." 2017.
- [33] "JSON." Accessed: Feb. 05, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.json.org/json-en.html>
- [34] E. Aras, A. Earthperson, and M. Diaconeasa, *Synthetic SAPH SOLVE Models*. (Oct. 2024). Zenodo. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13996736.
- [35] "Probabilistic Risk Assessment Group." Accessed: Apr. 30, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ne.ncsu.edu/prag/>
- [36] C. Ibáñez-Llano, A. Rauzy, E. Meléndez, and F. Nieto, "Hybrid approach for the assessment of PSA models by means of binary decision diagrams," *Reliab. Eng. Syst. Saf.*, vol. 95, no. 10, pp. 1076–1092, Oct. 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.ress.2010.04.016.
- [37] J. D. Andrews and S. J. Dunnett, "Event-tree analysis using binary decision diagrams," *IEEE Trans. Reliab.*, vol. 49, no. 2, pp. 230–238, Jun. 2000, doi: 10.1109/24.877343.
- [38] Z. Ma and J. Schroeder, "Event Tree Success Branch Modeling Approaches in SAPHIRE/SPAR," *Trans. Am. Nucl. Soc.*, vol. 110, 2014.
- [39] W. S. Jung, "A method to improve cutset probability calculation in probabilistic safety assessment of nuclear power plants," *Reliab. Eng. Syst. Saf.*, vol. 134, pp. 134–142, Feb. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.ress.2014.10.019.
- [40] Y. Dutuit and A. Rauzy, "Importance factors of coherent systems: A review," *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng. Part O J. Risk Reliab.*, vol. 228, no. 3, pp. 313–323, Jun. 2014, doi: 10.1177/1748006X13512296.
- [41] O. Nusbaumer and A. Rauzy, "Fault tree linking versus event tree linking approaches: a reasoned comparison," *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng. Part O J. Risk Reliab.*, vol. 227, no. 3, pp. 315–326, Jun. 2013, doi: 10.1177/1748006X13490260.
- [42] D. M. Rasmuson, "A comparison of the small and large event tree approaches used in PRAs," *Reliab. Eng. Syst. Saf.*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 79–90, Jan. 1992, doi: 10.1016/0951-8320(92)90062-P.
- [43] E. Choi, J.-G. Ha, D. Hahm, and M. K. Kim, "A review of multihazard risk assessment: Progress, potential, and challenges in the application to nuclear power plants," *Int. J. Disaster Risk Reduct.*, vol. 53, p. 101933, Feb. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.ijdrr.2020.101933.

- [44] “Great East Japan Earthquake.” Accessed: Jun. 06, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.who.int/westernpacific/emergencies/great-east-japan-earthquake>
- [45] “International Nuclear and Radiological Event Scale (INES) | IAEA.” Accessed: Jun. 11, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iaea.org/resources/databases/international-nuclear-and-radiological-event-scale>
- [46] J. Wang, Z. He, and W. Weng, “A review of the research into the relations between hazards in multi-hazard risk analysis,” *Nat. Hazards*, vol. 104, no. 3, pp. 2003–2026, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1007/s11069-020-04259-3.
- [47] M. S. Kappes, M. Keiler, K. von Elverfeldt, and T. Glade, “Challenges of analyzing multi-hazard risk: a review,” *Nat. Hazards*, vol. 64, no. 2, pp. 1925–1958, Nov. 2012, doi: 10.1007/s11069-012-0294-2.
- [48] J. H. Kim, M. K. Kim, and I.-K. Choi, “PRELIMINARY STUDY ON THE QUANTIFICATION OF COMPONENT LEVEL FAILURE FREQUENCY BY MULTI-HAZARD,” p. 6, 2019.
- [49] Y. Yu, X. Lv, and F. Niu, “Large LOCA accident analysis for AP1000 under earthquake,” *Ann. Nucl. Energy*, vol. 77, pp. 142–147, Mar. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.anucene.2014.11.013.
- [50] A. Prošek, A. Wielenberg, H. Löffler, and E. Raimond, “Methodology for selecting initiating events and hazards for consideration in an extended PSA,” in *Safety and Reliability – Theory and Applications*, High Tatras Mountains, Tatranské Matliare, Slovak Republic: CRC Press, Jun. 2017, pp. 490–490. doi: 10.1201/9781315210469-421.
- [51] J. Daniell, A. Schaefer, F. Wenzel, and E. Hacker, “Review of state-of-the art for hazard and multi-hazard characterisation,” 2810899, Apr. 2019.
- [52] “Home | NARSIS.” Accessed: Jul. 23, 2021. [Online]. Available: <http://www.narsis.eu/>
- [53] S. Kwag and D. Hahm, “Development of an earthquake-induced landslide risk assessment approach for nuclear power plants,” *Nucl. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 50, no. 8, pp. 1372–1386, Dec. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.net.2018.07.016.
- [54] S. Kwag and A. Gupta, “Probabilistic risk assessment framework for structural systems under multiple hazards using Bayesian statistics,” *Nucl. Eng. Des.*, vol. 315, pp. 20–34, Apr. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.nucengdes.2017.02.009.
- [55] H. Li, G. E. Apostolakis, J. Gifun, W. VanSchalkwyk, S. Leite, and D. Barber, “Ranking the Risks from Multiple Hazards in a Small Community,” *Risk Anal.*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 438–456, Mar. 2009, doi: 10.1111/j.1539-6924.2008.01164.x.
- [56] S. E. Cooper, J. Xing, and Y. J. Chang, “What HRA needs to support site-wide, multi-hazard Level 2-PRA,” presented at the ANS PSA 2013 International Meeting on Probabilistic Safety Assessment and Analysis, Columbia, SC: American Nuclear Society, Sep. 2013.
- [57] W. Hasselbring, “Benchmarking as Empirical Standard in Software Engineering Research,” in *Evaluation and Assessment in Software Engineering*, Trondheim Norway: ACM, Jun. 2021, pp. 365–372. doi: 10.1145/3463274.3463361.
- [58] *sosy-lab/benchexec*. (Jan. 22, 2024). Python. SoSy-Lab. Accessed: Feb. 02, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/sosy-lab/benchexec>

- [59] D. Beyer, S. Löwe, and P. Wendler, “Reliable benchmarking: requirements and solutions,” *Int. J. Softw. Tools Technol. Transf.*, vol. 21, no. 1, pp. 1–29, Feb. 2019, doi: 10.1007/s10009-017-0469-y.
- [60] “Robey and Zamora - Parallel and High Performance Computing.pdf.”
- [61] “Intel® VTune™ Profiler.” Accessed: Jan. 31, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/develop/documentation/vtune-help/top.html>
- [62] A. S. Farag, E. M. Aras, A. Earthperson, S. T. Wood, and J. Boyce, “Preliminary Benchmarking of SAPH SOLVE, XFTA, and SCRAM using Synthetically Generated Fault Trees with Common Cause Failures,” in *18th International Probabilistic Safety Assessment and Analysis (PSA 2023)*, Knoxville, TN: American Nuclear Society, 2023, pp. 40–49.
- [63] E. Aras, A. Earthperson, and M. Diaconeasa, *Synthetic Open-PSA Models*. (Oct. 2024). Zenodo. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13996371.
- [64] “Intel® Core™ i7-8700 Processor.” Accessed: Jan. 17, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/products/sku/126686/intel-core-i78700-processor-12m-cache-up-to-4-60-ghz/specifications.html>
- [65] “anders_melander / map2pdb — Bitbucket.” Accessed: Aug. 18, 2023. [Online]. Available: https://bitbucket.org/anders_melander/map2pdb/src/master/